

Lipid profile and fatty acid composition in eggs of Gangetic little barb *Puntius sophore* in comparison with body tissue lipid

Tapas Mukhopadhyay and Santinath Ghosh*

Department of Chemical Technology, Oil Technology Division, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : santinathghosh@yahoo.com.hk Fax : 91-33-23519755

Manuscript received 16 September 2004, accepted 20 May 2005

The lipid class and fatty acid composition in eggs of spot fin swamp little barb *Puntius sophore* has been studied in comparison with body tissue lipid. The eggs contain about 1.87 times higher lipid than that of the body tissue. The major portion of lipid in eggs is composed of phospholipid (PL) followed by triacylglycerol (TAG). But in the body tissue the major fraction is TAG followed by PL. Egg lipids are rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) of which major fractions are accumulated in PL fractions. The significant amount of phosphatidylinositol (PI) present both in egg and body tissue PL fractions rather than phosphatidylcholine (PC) and phosphatidylethanolamine (PE). The results of the study indicate that *P. sophore* eggs are rich in PUFA, which are very much important from nutritional point of view.

Puntius sophore (Hamilton-Buchanan), a very plentiful shoaling fish popularly known as little barb is most common in the fresh water ponds and rivers in the Gangetic provinces specifically in West Bengal basin.

In continuation of our study on the lipid profile and fatty acid composition on Indian fresh water fish eggs like *Cyprinus carpio*, *Notopterus notopterus*, *Glossogobius giuris* and *Mugil parsia*¹, in the present study, investigation has been made on the lipid profile of *Puntius sophore* eggs along with its body tissue to find out whether egg and body tissue lipids contain any important fatty acids in significant proportions, their nutritional significance in fish development and also in human beings on the basis of essential fatty acids present in both neutral lipid and PL fractions.

Results and discussion

Six different body tissue and egg samples of the respective individual gravid fish of *Puntius sophore* were analyzed separately. Total lipid content and their lipid class composition are cited in Table 1. Mean wet weight of matured eggs (2.4 ± 0.14) g accounts for 15.6% of total wet weight of fish. The lipid content of egg is about 13.1% (on dry basis) which is 1.9 times higher in comparison with body tissue lipid content (about 7.0%). The major portion of lipid in eggs is composed of phospholipid (PL, about 55.2%) followed by triacylglycerol (TAG, about 17.7%) and a trace amount of cholesterol (1.2%). But in the body tissue lipid, the major fraction is TAG (about 53.3%) followed by PL (about 22.5%) and very small amount of cho-

lesterol (0.4%). Besides, a noticeable amount of monoglycerides, diglycerides and fatty acids collectively called others (25.7% in egg and 23.8% in body tissue) are also observed.

Table 1. Lipid content and lipid class composition in eggs and body tissue of *Puntius sophore*

Total weight of fish (wet weight in g)	15.4 ± 0.77	
Weight of fish eggs (wet weight in g)	2.4 ± 0.14	
Moisture content in fish eggs (%)	54.9 ± 2.61	
Moisture content in body tissue (%)	71.4 ± 2.04	
Lipid content (% dry weight) in eggs	13.1 ± 1.48	
Lipid content (% dry weight) in tissue	7.0 ± 0.20	
Lipid class composition		
(% w/w of total lipid)	Eggs	Body tissue
Phospholipid (PL)	55.2 ± 1.73	22.5 ± 0.71
Cholesterol	1.2 ± 0.03	0.4 ± 0.02
Triacylglycerol (TAG)	17.7 ± 0.13	53.3 ± 1.32
Others (MG + DG + fatty acid)	25.7 ± 0.98	23.8 ± 1.61
Values are mean ± SE, n = 6.		

PLs present in the total lipid of both egg and body tissues are fractionated to determine the individual components (Table 2). Phosphatidylinositol (PI) is surprisingly abundant both in eggs (about 43.6%) and body tissue (about 48.1%) followed by phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) (31.2% in egg and 31.7% in body tissue) and phosphatidylcholine (PC) (25.2% in egg and 20.2% in body tissue). Besides these, a trace amount of phosphatidic acid (PA) and phosphatidylserine (PS) are observed both in eggs and body tissue.

PL is the major lipid fraction in eggs of *P. sophore*, where as TAG is the predominant fraction in body tissue lipid. Both in egg and body tissue PL, PI is the predominant fraction. PL content of egg is also related to the embryogenesis². It is believed that fish at early stages require PLs in their diet for proper development³. Geurden *et al.*⁴ showed that carp larvae responded distinctly to dietary PC to a PL free diet resulted in a high initial larval growth rate, but induced body deformities and subsequent mortalities, where as purified PI supported optimal survival and a minimal occurrence of abnormalities.

Calcium concentrations are also important in regulation of cellular mitosis⁵. A nutritional requirement for PL, especially for PC has been reported for fish larvae⁶. PC appears to be crucial in the formation of very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) during the intestinal absorption of neutral lipids and thus increases the amount of energy available for growth⁷. Frasher *et al.*² also showed that PC and PE were the source of metabolic energy and a source of essential fatty acid (EFA), organic phosphorous in eggs and larvae of Cod (*Gadus morhua*).

Table 2. Major phospholipid fractions (% w/w of total phospholipid) in eggs of Puntii (*Puntius sophore*)

Phospholipid fractions (% w/w of total phospholipid)	Eggs	Body tissue
Phosphatidylcholine (PC)	25.2 ± 1.38	20.2 ± 0.87
Phosphatidylinositol (PI)	43.6 ± 1.46	48.1 ± 1.33
Phosphatidylethanolamine (PE)	31.2 ± 1.65	31.7 ± 1.12

Values are mean ± SE, n = 6.

PI has been shown to be important in cell regulation due to its role as a precursor of inositol-tri-phosphate (IP₃), which activates an intracellular cascade, which in turn influences calcium release in the cell. Calcium release leads to a series of metabolic reactions in the newly fertilized egg, including activation of NAD-kinase for lipid biosynthesis, increased oxygen consumption, and increased pH.

Fatty acid composition of total lipid, TAG and PL fraction in eggs and body tissue are shown in Table 3. Among saturated fatty acids the most abundant is palmitic acid (16 : 0) both in body tissue (37.5%) and eggs (35%) lipid and concentrated mainly in TAG fractions. Among the monoenoic fatty acids oleic acid (18 : 1n-9) is higher and predominant component both in egg total lipid (32.2%) and body tissue total lipid (34.6%) than palmitoleic acid (16 : 1n-7). Among unsaturates, linoleic acid (18 : 2n-6 LA) and arachidonic acid (20 : 4n-6 AA) present as the only n-6 PUFAs in the total lipid, TAG and PL fractions of both egg and body tissue lipid of *P. sophore* and they are mainly concentrated in PL fractions. Total n-6 fatty acids in body tissue lipid is 12.7, 5.7 and 16.9% in total lipid, TAG and PL fractions where as in egg lipid it is 10.6, 6.8 and 14.3% respectively. Among the n-3 PUFAs both EPA and DHA

Table 3. Fatty acid composition of egg lipid and body tissue lipid of Puntii (*Puntius sophore*)

Fatty acids	Fatty acid composition (% w/w) in					
	Body tissue lipid			Egg lipid		
	Total	TAG	PL	Total	TAG	PL
14 : 0	1.8 ± 0.07	4.1 ± 0.10	0.6 ± 0.04	1.2 ± 0.13	2.9 ± 0.11	0.7 ± 0.08
16 : 0	32.4 ± 0.44	37.5 ± 0.20	26.9 ± 0.40	30.7 ± 0.18	35.0 ± 1.62	23.3 ± 0.67
18 : 0	6.3 ± 0.23	3.9 ± 0.04	8.0 ± 0.21	6.8 ± 0.23	8.6 ± 0.31	5.7 ± 0.45
Total	40.4 ± 0.54	45.5 ± 0.21	35.5 ± 0.51	38.8 ± 1.06	46.5 ± 1.85	29.7 ± 0.86
saturates						
16 : 1	2.2 ± 0.07	4.2 ± 0.09	0.8 ± 0.04	2.4 ± 0.55	5.4 ± 0.54	2.8 ± 0.14
18 : 1	34.6 ± 0.50	37.8 ± 0.26	25.0 ± 0.50	32.2 ± 0.88	24.3 ± 0.25	25.2 ± 0.62
20 : 1	0.5 ± 0.04	0.2 ± 0.04	0.2 ± 0.03	1.0 ± 0.88	1.2 ± 0.16	0.2 ± 0.04
Total mono	37.2 ± 0.51	42.3 ± 0.22	28.0 ± 0.47	35.6 ± 1.17	30.9 ± 0.80	28.3 ± 0.54
unsaturates						
18 : 2 (n-6)	8.0 ± 0.08	5.1 ± 0.10	7.3 ± 0.26	5.9 ± 0.20	4.4 ± 0.36	6.1 ± 0.37
20 : 2 (n-3)	0.8 ± 0.06	0.8 ± 0.04	0.5 ± 0.04	1.0 ± 0.10	1.0 ± 0.13	0.5 ± 0.09
18 : 3 (n-3)	0.5 ± 0.07	0.2 ± 0.03	0.2 ± 0.03	0.1 ± 0.03	0.1 ± 0.04	0.0
20 : 3 (n-3)	0.3 ± 0.05	0.2 ± 0.03	0.2 ± 0.04	0.7 ± 0.06	0.8 ± 0.10	1.2 ± 0.12
20 : 4 (n-6)	3.8 ± 0.09	0.7 ± 0.05	9.3 ± 0.40	4.7 ± 0.44	2.3 ± 0.25	8.2 ± 0.25
20 : 4 (n-3)	0.6 ± 0.05	0.3 ± 0.05	0.3 ± 0.05	1.1 ± 0.12	0.6 ± 0.03	1.6 ± 0.17
20 : 5 (n-3)	2.5 ± 0.08	1.2 ± 0.06	7.0 ± 0.21	2.5 ± 0.14	4.2 ± 0.51	4.3 ± 0.97
22 : 5 (n-3)	0.8 ± 0.06	0.8 ± 0.04	2.1 ± 0.07	0.8 ± 0.07	0.6 ± 0.05	4.6 ± 0.72
22 : 6 (n-3)	4.9 ± 0.12	2.5 ± 0.06	9.8 ± 0.38	9.1 ± 0.21	8.4 ± 0.45	15.6 ± 0.96
Total PUFA	22.2 ± 0.33	11.9 ± 0.26	36.8 ± 0.33	25.8 ± 0.42	22.5 ± 1.22	42.0 ± 0.95
(n-3) Total	9.8 ± 0.31	5.9 ± 0.17	20.2 ± 0.61	15.1 ± 0.42	15.8 ± 0.53	28.6 ± 1.02
(n-6) Total	12.7 ± 0.60	5.7 ± 0.22	16.9 ± 0.66	10.6 ± 0.40	6.8 ± 0.36	14.3 ± 0.48
(n-3)/(n-6)	0.8 ± 0.07	1.0 ± 0.08	1.2 ± 0.10	1.4 ± 0.13	2.3 ± 0.17	2.0 ± 0.19

Values are mean ± SE, n = 6.

content in egg lipid is higher than that of the components present in body tissue lipid. EPA and DHA in PL fraction of body tissue lipid are 7% and 9.8% where as in egg PL fraction they are about 4.3% and 15.6% respectively. Total PUFA is measured at about 42% in egg PL and 36.8% in body tissue PL fraction. The ratio of total n-3 to n-6 fatty acids is almost double in egg lipid (1.4) than the body tissue lipid (0.8) indicating the abundance of n-3 PUFAs in egg in contrast to body tissue of *P. sophore*.

Lipid is usually the primary form of energy stored in eggs and larvae in many fish species⁸. In the rapid development of larvae lipid particularly TAG reserves can be used to obtain the necessary metabolic energy to enhance the development. In the present study lipid content in the eggs is much higher than that in the body tissue. A significant amount of PL is present in eggs of this little barb. Among PL fractions, PI is surprisingly predominant both in egg and body tissue.

The health benefits of fish oil have been extensively investigated due to low incidence of coronary heart disease among populations who consume large amount of fish⁹. The active constituents of fish oil are mainly long-chain n-3 fatty acids, EPA and DHA. Several marine fish species are rich in n-3 PUFAs. Compared with marine fish, fresh water fish contain higher level of C₁₈ PUFA and also substantial amount of EPA and DHA¹⁰. The presence of significant amount of EPA and DHA in PL fraction of both egg and body tissue lipid of *P. sophore* also supports these observations. It is very distinct that major portion of these fatty acids are accumulated in the PL fraction. *P. sophore* along with its eggs may be used as a very good source of essential fatty acids from nutritional point of view. The gravid female barb *P. sophore* is nutritionally significant due to its high PL content and significant amount of n-3 PUFAs in addition to its delicious test.

Experimental

Fresh matured unfertilized eggs of *P. sophore* of six different living gravid females weighing about 15.4 g were collected during rainy season (spawning season) from fisherman in the time of netting at Sodepur, Kolkata, West Bengal, India. The eggs and body tissue samples from different body parts of the respective six fishes were collected and stored separately in glass vials containing chloroform/methanol (2 : 1, v/v) and 0.01% (w/w) butylatedhydroxy toluene (BHT) at -20°C prior to extraction.

The total lipid was extracted from body tissues and eggs individually by standard extraction method of Folch *et al.*¹¹. After extraction, chloroform was removed under a

stream of nitrogen and finally the lipid was dried under vacuum and stored separately at -20°C for analysis.

The isolated lipid was mainly a mixture of PL, cholesterol, TAG, DG, MG and fatty acid identified distinctly on TLC plate (silica gel G; solvent system, hexane/diethylether, 70 : 30, v/v) with phosphate stain, standard cholesterol, TAG, DG, MG in the same plate. The PL and TAG were separated on a preparative TLC plate (20 cm × 20 cm) with the above solvent system and the individual fractions were extracted with diethylether for preparation of methyl ester to determine their detail fatty acid composition.

The total fatty acid composition of the lipid and of the isolated TAG and PL were determined by GLC method after derivatization into methyl esters¹². The HP-5890A GLC (Hewlett-Packard) was connected with a glass column (183 cm × 0.31 cm i.d.) packed with 10% diethyleneglycol succinate (DEGS) supported on chromosorb-WHP (100/200 mesh) of HP make. The oven, injector and detector block temperatures were maintained at 190, 230 and 240°C respectively. IOLAR-2 nitrogen (BOC India Ltd., India) was used as carrier gas (flow rate 45 ml/min). The fatty acid esters peak were identified and calibrated with standard methyl ester (Sigma Chemical Co., USA).

Total PL content was measured following the standard method of A.O.C.S.¹³. Total cholesterol content was estimated according to the standard method of Zlatkis *et al.*¹⁴. Individual PL fractions were determined by fractionation with two-dimensional TLC followed by phosphorous measurement¹³. Total amount of TAG and other components like DG, MG and hydrocarbons were quantitatively estimated by standard column chromatography method¹⁵.

References

1. T. Mukhopadhyay and S. Ghosh, *J. Oleo Sci.*, 2003, **52**, 439; T. Mukhopadhyay, S. Nandi and S. Ghosh, *J. Oleo Sci.*, 2004, **53**, 323; T. Mukhopadhyay and S. Ghosh, *J. Food Sci. Technol.*, 2003, **40**, 502; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 192.
2. A. J. Fraser, J. C. Gamble and J. R. Sargent, *Mar. Biol.*, 1988, **99**, 307.
3. S. Teshima, A. Kanazawa, K. Horinouchi, S. Yamasaki and H. Hirata, *Nippon Suisan Gakkaishi*, 1987, **53**, 609; W. M. Koven, S. Kolkovski, A. Tandler, G. W. Kissil and D. Sklan, *Fish Physiol. Biochem.*, 1993, **10**, 357; P. Coutteau, I. Geurden, M. R. Camara, P. Bergot and P. Sorgeloos, *Aquaculture*, 1997, **155**, 149.
4. I. Geurden, N. Charlon, D. Marion and P. Bergot, *Aquacult. Int.*, 1997, **5**, 137; I. Geurden, D. Marion, N. Charlon, P. Coutteau and P. Bergot, *Aquaculture*, 1998, **161**, 225.
5. M. Whitaker and R. Patel, *Develop. Biol.*, 1990, **108**, 525.
6. A. Kanazawa, "Fish Nutrition in Practice" in : S. J. Kaushik and P. Luquet (eds.), *Les Colloques 61 ed.*, INRA, Paris, France, 1993.

- p. 519; I. Geurden, J. Radunz-Neto and P. Bergot, *Aquaculture*, 1995, **131**, 303.
7. F. J. Field and S. N. Mathur, *Prog. Lipid Res.*, 1995, **34**, 185; S. Fontagne, I. Geurden, A. -M. Escaffre and P. Bergot, *Aquaculture*, **161**, 213.
8. A. J. Fraser, J. R. Sargent, J. C. Gamble and P. MacLachlan, *Can. J. Fish Aquat. Sci.*, 1989, **46**, 1868.
9. R. G. Ackman, *Com. Biochem. Physiol.*, 1967, **22**, 907.
10. C. B. Cowey and J. R. Sargent, *Adv. Marine Biol.*, 1972, **10**, 383.
11. J. Folch, M. Lees and G. S. Stanley, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1957, **226**, 497.
12. L. D. Metcalfe and A. A. Schmitz, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, **33**, 363.
13. "Official Methods and Recommended Practice of American Oil Chemists' Society", 4th ed., D. Firestone, Washington DC, 1991, Method No. Ja 7-86 (Total Phospholipid); Ca 12-55 (Phospholipid Fractions).
14. B. Zlatkis, B. Zak and A. J. Boyle, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1953, **41**, 486.
15. M. Kates, "Techniques of Lipidology", North-Holland Publishing Company – Amsterdam, London. American Elsevier Publishing Company Inc., New York, 1972, p. 402.